

Transition metal complexes of bis(*s*-methyldithiocarbazate)resdiacetophenone

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The complexes of Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and VO^{II} with Schiff base derived from resdiacetophenone and *s*-methyldithiocarbazate have been synthesized. The Schiff base behaves as a bistridentate ligand coordinating through the deprotonated phenolic oxygen, azomethine nitrogen and thioenolic sulfur atoms with metal ion. All the complexes are non-electrolytic in nature. The thermogravimetric data have been analyzed for kinetic parameters using Freeman-Carroll, Sharp-Wentworth and Coats-Redfern methods and comparable values are obtained.

The synthetic and structural aspects of metal complexes of ligands derived from dithiocarbazic acid and its derivatives have received considerable attention¹. Dithiocarbazic acid and the Schiff bases derived from its *s*-alkyl esters form an interesting series of ligands, whose properties can be greatly modified by introducing organic substituents thereby inducing different stereochemistries in the resultant complexes. The literature survey revealed no report on the complexes of bis(*s*-methyldithiocarbazate)resdiacetophenone (BSMZRD), hence it was considered worthwhile and interesting to study the metal complexes derived from the Schiff base, BSMZRD.

Results and discussion

All the complexes (Table 1) are coloured solids, stable at room temperature, and insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in DMF and DMSO. Very low molar conductance values indicate their non-electrolytic nature². ¹H NMR spectrum of the ligand shows signals at δ 2.50–2.66, 2.93, 10.50, 12.33, 7.55–7.96 corresponding to CH_3 -C=N, SCH_3 , NH, OH (phenolic) and phenyl protons, respectively.

The IR ligand band at 1642 cm^{-1} (C=N) is shifted to lower frequency (15 – 40 cm^{-1}) in the spectra of the complexes, indicating participation of the azomethine nitrogen in coordination³. The N–N ligand band at 955 cm^{-1} is shifted to higher frequency in the spectra of the complexes,

suggesting coordination via azomethine nitrogen⁴. The ligand band at 2920 cm^{-1} (intramolecularly hydrogen bonded phenolic OH stretch)⁵ is absent in the complexes,

Table 1. Physical data of the complexes*

Compd.	Colour	Metal % : Found/(Calcd.)	Decomp. temp. °C	Λ_M $\Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2$ mol^{-1}
BSMZRD	Yellow	–	220 ^a	–
[(VO) ₂ L.2H ₂ O]	Brown	19.45 (20.13)	260	5.00
[MnL] ₂	Grey	13.25 (14.05)	310	4.15
[FeL] ₂	Red	13.40 (14.35)	230	4.80
[CoL] ₂	Pink	14.03 (14.93)	290	4.20
[NiL] ₂	Yellow	14.00 (14.87)	270	3.90
[Cu ₂ L.2H ₂ O]	Green	24.13 (25.41)	320	4.30
[Zn ₂ L.2H ₂ O]	Red	24.05 (24.26)	300	3.80
[Cd ₂ L.2H ₂ O]	Brown	34.93 (35.44)	310	4.00

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses ^aM.p., °C.

suggesting deprotonation of OH and coordination of oxygen with the metal ion, which is further confirmed by positive shift (25 – 75 cm^{-1}) in the ligand band at 1260 cm^{-1} (C–O phenolic stretch)⁶. The ligand spectrum does not display band at 2700 cm^{-1} (SH), suggesting that, in solid state, the Schiff base remains in the thioketo form, but in solution it may remain in thioketo and thiol tautomeric forms. IR spectra of the complexes do not reveal the 3045 cm^{-1} (NH) ligand band as this secondary amine nitrogen is involved in the thioenolization and consequent deprotonation on complexation⁷. The ligand band at 890 cm^{-1} (NHC=S) is absent in all the complexes, indicating coordination through thiol

sulfur⁸. In addition, all the complexes display bands at 550–610 (M–O), 470–526 (M–N) and 310–360 cm⁻¹ (M–S)⁹. In case of the VO^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes, the bands at 3400–3600, 1435–1536 and 750–800 cm⁻¹ are assigned to coordinated water molecules¹⁰. In oxovanadium complex a strong band at 887 cm⁻¹ (V=O) is observed.

The Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes exhibit magnetic moments of 5.85, 5.74, 3.77 and 3.07 B.M., respectively, consistent with high-spin octahedral structure¹². The electronic spectrum of the Mn^{II} complex shows three bands at 15700, 19100 and 26100 cm⁻¹, assignable to the transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g} + {}^4E_g(G)$, respectively, indicating octahedral geometry¹³. The ligand field parameters are found to be $Dq = 1570 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B = 485.70 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\beta = 0.506$, supporting the octahedral geometry for the Mn^{II} complex. The decrease in the B value suggests appreciable covalent character in the metal-ligand bonds. The Fe^{II} complex exhibits bands at 10500 and 25000 cm⁻¹ assigned to ${}^5T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^5E_g$ and charge transfer transitions, respectively, for octahedral geometry. The calculated value of ligand field parameters, $Dq = 1050 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B = 567.50 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\beta = 0.535$ and LFSE = 50 kJ mol⁻¹ support the octahedral geometry for Fe^{II} ion. The electronic spectrum of the Co^{II} complex exhibits bands at 9000, 16500 and 18500 cm⁻¹ assigned to the transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$, respectively, suggesting high-spin octahedral structure. The ligand field parameters, $Dq = 1009.10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B = 706 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\beta = 0.727$, $\beta^0 = 27.29\%$, $v_2/v_1 = 1.83$ and LFSE = 72.38 kJ mol⁻¹ indicate octahedral geometry for the Co^{II} complex. The Ni^{II} complex exhibits three bands at 10400, 16800 and 26000 cm⁻¹ due to transitions ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$, respectively, in an octahedral geometry. The calculated values of ligand field parameters, $Dq = 1040 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B = 773.33 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\beta = 0.716$, $\beta^0 = 28.40\%$, $\lambda = 155.26$, $v_2/v_1 = 1.62$ and LFSE = 159.73 kJ mol⁻¹ are in agreement with octahedral geometry. The reflectance spectrum of the Cu^{II} complex shows bands at 17500, 18200 and 25000 cm⁻¹, assignable to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ and charge transfer transitions, respectively. These transitions are observed in normally expected region for square-planar geometry¹⁴. The Cu^{II} complex has magnetic moment of 1.72 B.M., characteristic of square-planar structure. The VO^{II} complex has magnetic moment value of 1.64 B.M. Its diffuse reflectance spectrum shows bands at 10998, 16554 and 20425 cm⁻¹ due to the transitions ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$, ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$ and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$, respectively, characteristic of square-pyramidal geometry¹⁵. The Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes are found to be diamagnetic as expected and may have tetrahedral geometry¹⁶.

The TG curves show that the loss in weights in the Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes are negligible upto 210°, indicating absence of any water molecules. While the TG cur-

ves of the Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Cu^{II} and VO^{II} complexes show weight-loss of ~5.50, ~5.40, ~6.00 and 6.49%, respectively, at 150–210°, corresponding two coordinated water molecules. Thermal behavior of the complexes is almost the same and involve a major two-step decomposition after the loss of water molecules. The first step of decomposition is fast, as compared to the second step. This may due to the fact that the non-coordinated part of the ligand decomposes first (~250–350°), while the actually coordinated part decomposes later (~350–500°). The decomposition is complete at about 600° leading to the formation of metal oxides. The TG data of the decomposition of the complexes have been analyzed¹⁷ and the various kinetic and thermodynamic parameters are found to be very similar, indicating a common reaction mode¹⁸. The sequence of the thermal stability was found to be Ni > Cd > Mn > Zn > Co > Cu > Fe > VO > BSMZRD. The higher stabilities of the metal complexes than that of ligand may be due to the formation of stable five- and six-membered ring structures in the metal complexes.

Experimental

All the chemicals and metal salts used were of AnalaR grade. Resdiacetophenone was prepared by Friedel-Craft reaction. *S*-Methyldithiocarbamate was prepared by reported method¹⁹.

Schiff base (BSMZRD): A mixture of resdiacetophenone (0.01 mol) and *s*-methyldithiocarbamate (0.02 mol) dissolved separately in hot ethanol, was refluxed on a waterbath for ~4 h. On cooling, the yellow coloured product that separated out was crystallized from DMF and dried *in vacuo*, (70%), m.p. 220°. The ligand showed the expected elemental composition, IR and ¹H NMR spectra.

Metal complexes: An ethanolic/DMF solution (20 cm³) of BSMZRD (0.01 mol) was added to a methanolic solution (20 cm³) of the appropriate metal acetates (0.01 mol) [FAS, vanadyl sulfate and CdCl₂, were used in the preparation of Fe^{II}, VO^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes, respectively] with stirring. In case of the complexes of VO^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}, 1 : 2 molar ratio (L : M) was taken. The mixture was refluxed for 3–4 h. The product was washed with hot water, methanol, ethanol and DMF. The complexes were dried *in vacuo* over CaCl₂ at room temperature.

The elemental analyses were carried out by routine methods. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 842 spectrophotometer, ¹H NMR spectrum (CdCl₂/DMSO-*d*₆) using TMS as an internal standard on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer (90 MHz) and diffuse reflectance spectra on a Cary 2390 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature by Gouy method using Hg[Co(SCN)₄] as a calibrant. TG analyses were carried out on a laboratory set up apparatus in air at a

heating rate of $10^{\circ}/\text{min}^{-1}$ in the temperature range $40\text{--}700^{\circ}$. Molar conductance of the complexes in DMF were determined at room temperature using a Systronic 304 conductivity bridge.

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